

Pancreatic lipoma: A benign incidental Tumor

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Abstract

Pancreatic lipoma is a rare tumor discovered incidentally in the majority of cases during a CT scan. The knowledge of which may prove useful in removing diagnostic uncertainties and avoiding unnecessary surgical interventions in the event of a benign tumor.

It has characteristic imaging features so that histological biopsy sample is not needed for a definite diagnosis.

Keywords: Pancreas; Lipoma; Imaging; Adenocarcinoma

1. Introduction

Pancreatic lipoma is a very rare benign mesenchymal tumor of the pancreas. A computed tomography scan can make the diagnosis accurately. This tumor is typically detected incidentally on cross-sectional images. Recognition of radiological features of pancreatic lipoma is essential to avoid unnecessary investigation and procedures.

2. Case Presentation

We present the case of a 55-year-old male who presented with nausea and vomiting.

Abdominal examination revealed a soft and lax abdomen with no tenderness or palpable masses. Bowel sounds were of normal intensity and frequency. Examination of other systems revealed normal findings. Routine laboratory investigations did not reveal any abnormalities.

He underwent an abdominal CT scan which identified a pancreatic lipoma. Plain and contrast CT scanning of the abdomen ([Fig. 1](#)) demonstrated a well-defined, homogeneous, fatty (−89 HU) lesion measuring 5.7×8.6 mm with no contrast enhancement, on the body of the pancreas without infiltration of peripancreatic fatty tissue and no widening of the pancreatic duct and common bile duct.

3. Discussion

The most frequent pancreatic cancer is adenocarcinoma, constituting 85% of all cases. Tumours other than ductal carcinoma constitute 5–15% of cases and mesenchymal are rare and constitute less than 2%, with those containing fat being the most uncommon. The pancreas is an unusual location for a lipoma, which is usually detected as an incidental finding on imaging. Lipomas show characteristic imaging features, the identification of which allows the correct diagnosis without the need for histopathological confirmation.

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Lipomas are formed from mature fatty tissue surrounded by a fibrous capsule. In the human body lipomas occur in locations where fatty tissue is present; in the abdomen, most frequently in the digestive tract.

Mainly asymptomatic, . However, short-term interval observation is recommended to ascertain stability and help differentiate between pancreatic lipoma and early well-differentiated liposarcoma . Extensive follow-up is not necessary . Surgical removal of the lesion is not recommended.

Figure 1 Computed tomography obtained after intravenous administration of iodinated contrast material shows a well-defined, homogeneous, encapsulated tumor (arrow) with a negative HU values consistent with fat content.

4. Conclusions

Lipomas are rare, small, homogenous and well-circumscribed pancreatic tumours. The most important feature, decisive for the diagnosis and distinguishing them from pancreatic carcinoma, is detection of fatty tissue on CT and MR scans.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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